

Effect of Locomotor Training with A Robotic-Gait Orthosis (Lokomat) in Spasticity Modulation Of Spastic Hemiplegic Children: A Randomized Controlled Trial

Wpływ treningu ruchowego z użyciem zautomatyzowanej ortezy do oceny i nauki chodu (lokomat) w modulacji spasty czności u dzieci z hemiplegią spasty czną: randomizowane badanie kontrolowane

Mohamed Serag Eldein Mahgoub^{1(A,B,C,D,E,F)}, **Wagdy William Amin**^{2,3(A,C,D,E,F)},
Samah Saad Zahran^{4(A,C,D,E,F)}

¹Basic Sciences Department, Faculty of Physical Therapy, Cairo University, Egypt

²Department of Physical Therapy for Disturbance of Growth and Development in Pediatric and it is Surgeries, Faculty of Physical Therapy, Deraya University, Egypt

³Physical Therapy Department Sector of Medical Services, Ministry of Interior, Egypt

⁴Physical Therapy Department for Musculoskeletal Disorders and their Surgery, Faculty of Physical Therapy, Cairo University, Egypt

Abstract

Background. Studying robotic-assisted locomotor training (lokomat) in spasticity modulation in cerebral palsied hemiplegic children is a strategy for determining its efficacy in reducing spasticity

Objective. To investigate the efficacy of robotic-assisted locomotor training (lokomat) in spasticity modulation.

Methods. Thirty spastic hemiplegic cerebral palsied children of both genders ranged in age from 7 to 14 years contributed in this study, they were being randomly selected from a comprehensive rehabilitation center and assigned into two equal groups (15 children each). Control group (A) underwent traditional exercise treatment, while Study group (B) underwent lokomat gait training in addition to traditional exercise program. Lokomat training was performed 3 days/week for 12 weeks with up to 45 minutes of training per session. The 3-D kinematics gait analysis was carried out before and after intervention and used as an indicator for improvement and reduction of spasticity.

Results. there was a statistically significant improvement in the study group in comparison to control group.

Conclusion. Lokomat gait training is an effective additional tool for physical therapy program in treatment of hemiparetic C.P children as it plays an important role in decreasing spasticity and improving patient gait pattern.

Key words:

cerebral palsy, spasticity, 3-D measurement, Lokomat gait training

Streszczenie

Informacje podstawowe. Badanie dotyczące treningu lokomotorycznego z użyciem robota (lokomat) w modulacji spasty czności u dzieci z porażeniem mózgowym i porażeniem pofowicznym jest strategicznie określania jego skuteczności w zmniejszaniu spasty czności.

Cel. Zbadanie skuteczności treningu lokomotorycznego z użyciem robota (lokomat) w modulacji spasty czności. **Metody.** W badaniu wzięło udział 30 dzieci ze spasty cznym porażeniem pofowicznym, obu płci, w wieku od 7 do 14 lat. Dzieci zostały losowo wybrane z ośrodka kompleksowej rehabilitacji i przydzielone do dwóch równych grup (po 15 dzieci). Grupa kontrolna (A) była poddawana tradycyjnej terapii ruchowej, natomiast grupa badana (B) oprócz tradycyjnego programu ćwiczeń była poddawana treningowi chodu przy użyciu robota lokomat. Trening przy użyciu lokomatu był wykonywany 3 dni w tygodniu przez 4 tygodnie, maksymalnie 45 minut na sesję. Analiza kinematyki chodu 3-D została przeprowadzona przed i po interwencji, i wykorzystana jako wskaźnik poprawy i zmniejszenia spasty czności.

Wyniki. W grupie badanej nastąpiła istotna statystycznie poprawa w porównaniu z grupą kontrolną.

Wniosek. Trening chodu z użyciem lokomatu jest skutecznym dodatkowym narzędziem programu fizjoterapeutycznego w leczeniu dzieci z mózgowym porażeniem pofowicznym, ponieważ odgrywa ważną rolę w zmniejszaniu spasty czności i poprawie wzorca chodu pacjenta.

Słowa kluczowe:

porażenie mózgowe, spasty czność, pomiar 3-D, trening chodu z użyciem lokomatu

Introduction

One of the most frequently asked questions by the cerebral palsy parents is when my child will walk? Or my child will walk again? The reason for emphasis on the task of walking apart from many other abilities is that is more functional. The goal for many pediatric therapists is to help the cerebral palsy child to walk independently [1].

Cerebral palsy (CP) is defined as a clinical syndrome characterized by a persistent disorder of posture or movement due to a non-progressive disorder of the immature brain. The most common movement disorder in CP is a spastic paresis, defined as a posture and movement dependent tone regulation disorder. The clinical manifestation of spastic paresis varies widely, depending on the various impairments of muscle function that can be distinguished. Clinical symptoms of impaired muscle function can either be related to an impairment of muscle can activation or to a change in biomechanical properties of muscles and connective tissues [2].

Spastic hemiplegia is a unilateral paresis with upper limbs more severely affected than the lower limbs. It is seen in 56% of term infant and 17% of preterm infants and pathogenesis is multifactorial. Voluntary movements are impaired with hand function being most affected. In the lower limb, dorsi flexion and eversion of the foot are most impaired. There is increase in flexor tone with hemiparetic posture, flexion at the elbow and wrist, knee extension and equines position of the foot [3].

Research has shown that children with CP (spastic hemiplegic and diaplegia) must take a step at lower platform displacement velocities than typically developing children of the same age, take a longer time to recover stability and show more center of pressure movement during the recovery period as well [4]. Robotic-assisted gait training (lokomat) affords an opportunity to increase walking practice with mechanical assistance from robotic devices, rather than therapists, where the child may not be able to generate a sufficient or correct motion with enough repetitions to promote gait improvement [5].

Robotic assisted gait training (lokomat) has become an increasingly common rehabilitation tool over the last decade to improve the gait pattern of people with neurological impairment [5].

Nevertheless, it is commonly accepted today that lokomat training can be integrated into the normal therapy program and has proven to be feasible for treatment of several different pathologies such as spinal cord injury, stroke, multiple sclerosis and cerebral palsy [6].

The current study aimed to determine the effectiveness of robotic-assisted locomotor (lokomat) training in controlling plantar flexors spasticity and consequently improving patient's gait pattern.

There is limited research studying the effect of Lokomat gait training in spasticity modulation on cerebral palsied hemiplegic children and there is no research studying its intermediate effect. Do Lokomat gait training improve patient gait pattern and decrease spasticity in cerebral palsied hemiplegic children.

Materials and Methods

Study design

The design of the study was pre-test post-test randomized controlled trail design. The procedures followed agreed with the Institutional Ethical Committee Clearance, and written informed consent was taken from their legal guardians of the children. Pan

African Clinical Trial Registry number is (PACTR201901582864286).

Participants

This study was conducted in the laboratories of EDEN physical therapy center from January to September 2019 with simple random sample. Forty six spastic hemiplegic CP children with ages ranged from 7 to 14 years old were assessed for eligibility. Thirty children spastic hemiplegic CP (14 left sided and 16 right sided) of both sexes (16 B -14G) were randomly selected from comprehensive rehabilitation center and assigned randomly into two equal groups (15 child each).

All participants were included to this study if They had grade 1 or 1+ according to modified Ashworth scale and grade II or III according to Manual Ability Classification Scale (MACS), they understand and follow verbal commands and instructions included in the test, and they had no sensory impairment or other neurological or psychological problems other than mild perceptual defects. All participants were excluded to this study if children with any other neurological deficits such as convulsions, involuntary movements or receiving muscle relaxants, children with impairment of sensation (superficial, deep and cortical), Children with any other diseases such as cardiac disease and with severe mental retardation (IQ not less than 50), children with anatomical leg length discrepancy (lokomat limitation) exceeding 2 cm, fixed contracture, bone and joint deformities, bone articular instability (joint dislocation), Hip, knee, ankle arthrodesis, inflammation of skin and open skin lesion around the trunk or limb.

Randomization

Forty-six participants were assessed for eligibility. Thirty spastic hemiplegic CP children underwent randomization as in the flowchart (Fig. 1). Participants were randomly assigned into two groups. Simple randomization was used to assign the children into two groups of equal numbers by creating random digits from odd and even numbers. Each child was asked to blindly draw a piece of paper containing a hidden digit from a case; odd numbers were assigned to the control group whereas even numbers were assigned to the study group.

Intervention

Children's in control Group (A) consisted of 15 children (10 B and 5 G) were received traditional exercise treatment. Children's in study Group (B) consisted of 15 children (6 B and 9 G) were received lokomat gait training in addition to traditional exercise program. Individual exercises in both groups were aimed at improving motor control, increasing stability in upright positions and developing walking skills. Both groups participated in 12 weeks and the overall times assigned in both groups are the same.

Procedures

a) Assessment procedures: The assessors were blind folded to group allocation.

Fig 1. Flow chart of the participants

I - weight and height assessment: The weight and height of both groups were measured by the Hanson professional scale before the intervention [7].

II - Modified Ashworth scale: it was used for spasticity assessment for inclusion criteria.

III - The pro-reflex system.

This system that is used to evaluate gait parameters (ankle joint angle at initial contact, stride length, cadence and speed) as outcome measures and included the Q-Trac Software which consists of camera system with three cameras, reflective dots, a wand-Kit used for calibration of the system, and eight meters long walkway, a personal computer with installed Q Trac software (Made in Sweden).

(1) Setup: This step included three main points

Preparation of patient

The patient was asked to take off his/her cloths to expose both lower limbs up to pelvis. Seven reflective dots were placed on the selected bony landmarks by sticky material (at hip, supra patellar, knee, tibial tuberosity, ankle, heel and toes).

1) Hip: At the greater trochanter.

2) Supra patellar: Along the central line of the patella at the rectus femoris tendon, 1 cm proximal to the superior border of patella when the knee was extended. The medial and lateral edges of the patella were palpated, then the superior border of the patella was determined, and the marker was applied halfway between its edges and approximately 1 cm superior to patella.

3) Knee joint line: The lateral knee joint line was determined via the lateral tubercle of the tibia. The width of lateral aspect of the knee, when the patella was excluded was divided into two equal parts and the marker was applied in middle at the knee joint

line.

4) Tibial tuberosity: The marker was applied at tuberosity of tibia.

5) Ankle: At the lateral malleolus, 30 millimeters proximally to the lateral malleolus along the fibula. This marker was used as the camera had difficulties to distinguish the heel and ankle markers from each other.

6) Heel: At the heel, on the posterior aspect of the calcaneus, at the same horizontal plane as the toe marker.

7) Toe: at the foot between the second and third metatarsals, 10-15 millimeters proximal to the metatarsal heads. Each patient was asked to stand at the border of the measurement area, where the dots were visible in the cameras. Then the patient was asked to walk at the middle of the selected measurement area in which he or she was captured.

Camera Placement

The three cameras which were used in capturing the patient motion were arranged on one side of the 8 meters long walkway at a height of 1.5 to 2 meters. The patient stood midway on the walkway, to ensure that all cameras view the patient.

Measurement area

The Measurement area is the part on the walkway that the patient would walk along, it is about three meters that required performing three complete gait cycles. Primarily, the measurement area was marked on the wooden walkway by placing four reflected dots at the four corners of the selected distance of the walkway, which had to be visible in the cameras during the setup.

(2) Calibration

Before any three-dimensional (3-D) capture performance, the camera system was calibrated to assure accuracy of the obtained values. This calibration required these tools: A wand to provide the camera system with the measurement points to be used for the calibration. A reference structure for defining the calibration coordinate system. The reference structure was placed horizontally along the floor in the measurement area which is covered by the cameras. All cameras viewed the four markers of the structure. Once all parameters are correctly set up, the calibration performed by pressing the capture button and moving the wand around in the measurement volume during the calibration data retrieval. During the calibration capture, the wand was positioned in the three dimensions, starting with Z, X then Y directions respectively.

(3) Capture

A new file was opened for each patient including subject data (name, age, weight, height). The patient was asked to start walking from the starting point which was determined previously. When the patient passed the measurement starting position, the Q Trac measurement was started. The patient was instructed to continue walking to the end of the walkway until the Q Trac measurement is completed. The capture was initiated by selecting capture from the menu bar and the measurement should be saved.

(4) Export

It is the transfer of the selected gait cycles to the tabulated separated values (TSV) file for analysis. Data Processing included

two main steps.

1) Tracking of motion of the patient and names the skin dots each by its position on each landmark.

2) Selection of three complete gait cycles and export of this selection to the analysis file.

(5) Analysis

Dots used for the calculations were then identified. Finally, the calculations were initiated with the run button. When the calculations were completed, the results were displayed showing the calculated global gait parameters in tables and figures. The above evaluation procedures were done for each patient before treatment and after 3 months.

b) Training procedures

I - Group (A): received traditional exercise program (Stretching exercises, neurodevelopment technique (Bo- bath approach), strengthening exercises, balance and gait training exercises). This program was done in approximately one hour, three times per week for 12 successive weeks [8, 9].

II - Group (B): received lokomat gait training in addition to traditional exercise program. Lokomat training was performed 3 days/week during a 1-hour period including set-up time with up to 30 minutes of training during a single session. Treadmill speed was started as low as 0.5 kmph and increased up to 1 kmph as tolerated. Total training time, speed, distance and amount of loading will be recorded during each session. The training was provided for 12 weeks and subjects were evaluated before and after treatment. To further increase patient's engagement and motivation, virtual reality and computer game technique was used to provide virtual environment that encourage active participation during treatment, the LOKOMAT (Lokomat System V5.0. Hocoma AG. Industriestrasse 4CH-8604 Volketswil Switzerland), a robotic gait orthosis, was used to train the subjects in gait pattern. The motorized exoskeleton is attached to the patient's knee and hip and a spring-loaded stirrup supports the ankle, while a harness for the torso and pelvis provides dynamic body weight support. The degree to which the exoskeleton assists the gait can be adjusted in real-time by the therapist, as per subject's ability and comfort. The knee and hip joints are controlled by position and force sensors, which allow for individual adjustments [10].

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS software for Windows, version 21.0 (Chicago, IL, United States). Descriptive statistics were calculated for both groups before and after 3 months. Shapiro-Wilk's test was used to check the normal distribution of data. Two-way mixed model with the time within subject factor and treatment between subject factor, were utilized to determine any differences within and between groups regarding the degree of gait parameters (cadence, speed, step length and stride length) and ankle joint angle at initial contact were measured using three-dimensional analysis system [11]. The F value was used based on Wilks' lambda, and when the multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) demonstrated a significant effect, a follow-up univariate analysis of variance (ANOVA), a group-by-time two-way mixed model MANOVA with time as the repeated factor, was performed at $P = 0.01$ to protect against the possibility of the type I error.

Results

This study is concerned in determining the effectiveness of lokomat gait training in modulating plantar flexors spasticity. Clinical, functional and laboratory assessment data were collected from the control group (A) who received traditional exercise treatment program for hemiplegic cerebral palsy, and the study group (B) who received the lokomat gait training in

addition to traditional exercise treatment program given to the control group.

There was no significant difference between groups in age, weight and height ($P > 0.05$) as illustrated in table 1. There was no significant difference between both groups in gender distribution as the Chi-squared value was 0.53 ($P > 0.05$).

Table 1. Basic characteristics of participants

Variables	Control Group Mean \pm SD	Study Group Mean \pm SD	P-value
Age [year]	10.7 \pm 3.4	10.4 \pm 3.5	0.36
Height [cm]	138.3 \pm 18	139.8 \pm 16	0.62
Weight [kg]	45.3 \pm 21	46.8 \pm 22	0.73

SD: Standard deviation, P-value: Level of significance

Repeated measures multivariate analysis was conducted to assess the comparison between control group (A) and study group (B) also conducted before and after the treatment as regards the degree of stride length, cadence, speed, and ankle joint angle at initial contact. Significant multivariate effects were found for the main effects of treatment, Wilk's $\Lambda = 0.299$, $F(4,25) = 14.652$, $P < 0.0001$, $\eta^2 = 0.701$ and time, Wilk's $\Lambda = 0.033$, $F(4,25) = 182.748$, $P < 0.0001$, $\eta^2 = 0.967$, as well as for the interaction between treatment and time, Wilk's $\Lambda = 0.165$, $F(4,25) = 31.694$, $P < 0.0001$, $\eta^2 = 0.835$. Follow-up univariate ANOVAs reveal that significant changes for speed outcome variable, $F(1,28) = 2.952$, $P < 0.097$, $\eta^2 = 0.095$, for cadence outcome variable, $F(1,28) = 1.721$, $P < 0.200$, $\eta^2 = 0.058$, for Stride length outcome variable, $F(1,28) = 34.264$, $P < 0.0001$, $\eta^2 = 0.550$ and for ankle joint angle outcome variable, $F(1,28) = 17.152$, $P < 0.0001$, $\eta^2 = 0.380$. This interaction effect indicates that the difference between the control group (A) and study group (B) on the linear combination of the four dependent variables is different at pretest than posttest. Examination of the means suggests that this is because groups do not differ on either dependent variable at the time of the pretest, but they do differ at the time of the posttest. Study group (B) showed superiority to control group (A) after three months of intervention on cadence, speed, stride length and ankle joint angle index ($P < 0.0001$), as shown in Table 2.

Discussion

The current study was conducted to explore the effect of lokomat training in spasticity modulation for hemiplegic cerebral palsied children after three months of treatment. The results obtained from this study clearly demonstrated the positive effects of using robotic-assisted locomotor training in addition to the physical therapy program in decreasing spasticity of calf muscle and thus improving gait pattern in hemiplegic cerebral palsied children more than the physical therapy program alone. Selecting the study sample to be from hemiplegic children agrees with Wildson, [12] who stated that hemiplegia constitutes a major form among spastic type of cerebral palsy. It accounts about one third of all cerebral palsied cases as result of unilateral brain lesion. This also comes in agreement with Gromly 2001 who reported that hypertonia, in hemiplegia, contributes to muscle weakness, incoordination and limitation in range of motion [13].

Normally, children walk with a rapid cadence. It has been reported that the mean value of cadence at the age of one year is about 170 steps/minute. It decreases with age but still around 140 steps/minute at the age of seven. The higher cadence partly compensates for the short stride length, and the velocity ranges from 0.64 meters/second at the age of one year to 1.14 meters/second at the age of seven years [14].

This observation come in agreement with Sheridan [15] who states that during walking, the unaffected side of the hemiple-

Table 2. Outcome data for speed, cadence, stride length and ankle joint angle before and after intervention for control and study groups

Outcomes	Control group (n = 15)	Study group (n = 15)	Mean difference	99% Confidence interval	P-value
Speed pre	0.4733 ± 0.0798	0.4467 ± 0.0915	0.027	(-0.060, 0.113)	0.403
Speed post	0.5867 ± 0.0915	0.7200 ± 0.1146	-0.133	(-0.238, -0.029)	0.001
P-value	0.0001	0.0001			
Cadence pre	130.00 ± 3.964	130.73 ± 5.560	-0.733	(-5.606, 4.139)	0.681
Cadence Post	125.00 ± 4.225	119.93 ± 5.105	5.067	(0.338, 9.795)	0.006
P-value	0.0001	0.0001			
Stride Pre	0.3800 ± 0.0774	0.4000 ± 0.0845	-0.020	(-0.102, 0.062)	0.505
Stride Post	0.5067 ± 0.0703	0.7400 ± 0.0985	-0.233	(-0.320, -0.147)	0.0001
P-value	0.0001	0.0001			
Ankle angle pre	-2.7267 ± 1.081	-2.7173 ± 0.9047	-0.009	(-1.016, 0.997)	0.980
Ankle angle post	-1.3600 ± 0.6467	1.5560 ± 2.293	-2.916	(-4.616, -1.216)	0.0001
P-value	0.012	0.0001			

Data are mean ± SD; P-value < 0.01 indicates statistical significance

gic child obviously takes all or most of the child's weight. The hemiplegic lower limb may be adducted, internally rotated, knee extended, foot flat or in equines and toes may claw the ground. Because physical therapy is concerned with resolution of function, quantifying functional progress by assessing clinical changes in motor function in children with cerebral palsy is important, though it is complex task. The accurate detection of changes in function is the essential purpose of an evaluation outcome measure [16].

The post treatment results of this study revealed significant improvement in the mean value of all measuring variables of control group receiving traditional exercise program. This significant improvement may be attributed to the effect of traditional exercise program especially neurodevelopmental approach which was directed toward inhibiting the abnormal muscle tone and abnormal postural reflexes, facilitating normal pattern of postural control (righting and equilibrium reaction), developing a greater variety of normal movement patterns particularly in the

trunk and lower extremities. Also, developing weight shift and reciprocal coordinated movement of the lower limbs, providing postural adapting and finally to use these adaptable motor patterns as a basis for the development of skilled functional abilities [17].

This comes in agreement with Cramer and Riley [18], who reported that Stroke and traumatic brain or spinal cord injury result in neurological disorders associated with impaired or total loss of locomotion. Patients show clinical symptoms of flaccid paresis or spasticity in one or both legs. Basic research studies in the animal model including the cat have shown that repetitive execution of the impaired movement (supported by any external help) can improve motor function of the affected limbs. Research indicates that these improvements are based on neuroplasticity of the central nervous system at many levels and result in compensation for the loss of lesioned brain or spinal cord areas.

These findings are in line with the findings of recent research work done by Fernandes et al. [19], who stated that Cerebral

palsy children carrying spastic diplegia increase their capacity to generate strength when submitted to a resistive training not only on lower limbs but also on upper limbs. Furthermore, several studies have shown that diaphragic CP children improve their motor ability due to strength training, though it remains to be proved that strength training leads to a substantial change for the better allowing that there is ascension of category for functional capacity.

In addition, it comes in agreement with Gharlene and Johnna [20], who reported that according to the Bobath, the motor problems of CP arise fundamentally from CNS dysfunction which interferes with the development of normal postural control against gravity and impedes normal motor development. Handling techniques that controlled various sensory stimuli were used to inhibit spasticity, abnormal reflexes, and abnormal movement pattern, and were used to facilitate normal muscle tone, equilibrium responses, and movement pattern.

In the present study, our choice to use stretching exercises was supported by Yasser et al. [21], who reported that prolonged standing imposed stretch on the plantar flexor muscles and resulted in improvement ankle dorsiflexion during mid-stance. Improvement in this impairment may have resulted in greater excursion of the ankle and foot throughout the stance phase. Allowing the subject to assume better foot alignment, thus enabling proper placement of the foot on the ground for weight acceptance during stance phase.

These findings are in agreement with Adam et al. [22], who reported that functional gait training is a safe, feasible, and effective intervention to target improved walking ability in children and young adults with CP. The addition of virtual reality and biofeedback can increase patient engagement and magnify effects.

Concerning the results of physical therapy program group, the results of our study come in agreement with Maria et al. [23], who stated that daily intensive gait training increases beta and gamma oscillatory central drive to ankle dorsiflexor motor neurons and that it improves toe lift and heel strike in children with cerebral palsy. We propose these findings indicate that intensive gait training produces plastic changes in the corticospinal tract and that the resulting increase in central drive is responsible for improvements in gait function.

On the other hand, the application of Lokomat training in addition to traditional exercise program applied to children in the study group of the present study revealed highly significant improvement in the treatment mean values of all the measuring variables, which indicated highly significant difference improvement when compared with results of the control group. In the present study, selecting Lokomat training in addition to traditional exercise program come in agreement with Mirbagheri [24], who documented that Lokomat training can be more efficient in modifying neuromuscular abnormalities associated with spasticity than anti-spastic medication (Tizanidine). Also, they revealed that Lokomat training is effective in reducing spasticity and improving volitional control in spinal cord injury [25]. Properties in neurologically impaired subjects thus facilitate greater recovery. Further, this study shows that the system identification technique can be effective method to characterize the progress of neuromuscular modification during treatment in spastic population [26].

Furthermore, Westlake and Patten [27], published systematic

reviews examined the effects of partial body weight supported treadmill training in individuals with CP, spinal cord injury and acquired brain injury. Several studies have demonstrated improvements in locomotor ability in different patient population receiving robot-assisted gait training. In addition, it comes in agreement with Mac Kay [28], who reported that since higher brain centers are often damaged in children with cerebral palsy, it is assumed that central pattern generators activation and automatic reciprocal mechanisms play an important role in stimulating walking through locomotor training.

Our findings are in line with the findings of recent research work done by Sophie et al. [5], They stated that robotic-assisted gait training (Lokomat) affords an opportunity to increase walking practice with mechanical assistance from robotic devices, rather than therapists, where the child may not be able to generate enough or correct motion with sufficient repetitions to promote gait improvement.

Wirz et al. [29], stated in their study that Lokomat training can effectively increase walking capacity by improving gait speed and endurance. It can be effective in reducing the neuromuscular abnormality that is associated with spastic hypertonic that typically arise after spinal cord injuries.

Our results come in agreement with Andreas et al. [30], who reported that children with CP benefit from robotic-assisted gait training in improving functional gait parameters so driven gait orthosis training offers a promising treatment option for improvement of walking abilities in children with cerebral palsy. At last, the results of present study supported by Pajaro et al. [31], who stated that robotic-assisted gait training (RGT) in children with CP results in improvements in walking speed and walking endurance. The study was limited for high cost of Lokomat gait training devices and limited number of cases for the study.

Conclusion

Lokomat gait training is a favorable effective additional tool to physical therapy program in treatment of hemiparetic C.P. children than the physical therapy program alone as it plays an important role in decreasing spasticity and improving patient gait pattern.

Adres do korespondencji / Corresponding author

Mohamed Serag Eldein

E-mail: drsergany_79@hotmail.com

Pismiennictwo/ References

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Rectification / Sprostowanie

Please be advised that the article "The role of physiotherapy in the treatment of dysfunctions and diseases of the temporomandibular joints" (*Fizjoterapia Polska*.3 / 2020 pp. 36-44) incorrectly contains the name of one of the authors. The paper edition includes: "Helena Sobczak", and it should be: "**Hanna Sobczak**".

Informujemy, iż artykule "Rola fizjoterapii w leczeniu dysfunkcji i chorób stawów skroniowo-zuchwowych" (Fizjoterapia Polska nr 3/2020 str. 36-44) błędnie zostało zamieszczone imię jednego z autorów. W wydaniu papierowym znajduje się: "Helena Sobczak", a powinno być: "**Hanna Sobczak**".